

УДК 378.311

COMPONENTS OF PUBLIC RELATIONS COMPETENCY OF FUTURE MANAGERS

S. O. Morhunova

*Kharkiv National Automobile and Highway University,
(Kharkiv Ukraine)*

E-mail: morgan.sa@mail.ru

КОМПОНЕНТИ PR-КОМПЕТЕНЦІЇ МАЙБУТНІХ МЕНЕДЖЕРІВ

С. О. Моргунова

*Харківський національний автомобільно-дорожній університет
(Харків, Україна)*

The essence of the notion «PR-competence» as a part of the competence of a future manager is identified in the article. Taking into account the notions of PR (relations with community) and professional competency, the author provides her own definition of PR-competency as an integral complex of the professional and behavioral qualities of personality, as a benchmark of major psychological and PR-concepts, as an index of human capacity to effectively use contemporary psychological and PR-technologies that enable a specialist to implement their knowledge into practice. The researcher states that PR-competency will be especially important for future managers because the range of the professional tasks of a specialist in this field includes the control of an enterprise image, the promotion of products at the market, relations with customers and mass media, the creation of the right image of enterprise and its internal corporate medium. On the basis of analysis of scientific approaches to the concept of PR-competence and its content, the unit of the core competencies, which includes two clusters: a group of key (common) and a group of special (professional) competencies, a combination of which consists the PR-competence of a future manager.

Key words: public relations, competency-related approach, competency, competence, PR-competency.

Problem statement. The current process of the modernization of the higher education in Ukraine, its integration into the European educational space and orientation towards economic systems of the developed countries of the world puts new requirements in terms of professional activities to train future managers. In the modern world public relations are an important component of any company. They contribute to the solution of a wide range of issues, first of all, to establish and support communication, to understand each other, to provide cooperation between a company and the general public. So, inclusion to the content of the educational process the of component that will contribute to the formation of personality, who is able to competently perform management activity, establish mutually beneficial relations between the institution and the public is topical. This component should be PR-competency of a future manager.

At present, the higher education system of Ukraine witnesses a stable tendency to introduce a competency-based approach to form and organize an educational process. Educational results and priorities are shifting from achievement of concrete knowledge and skills towards having a constellation of competencies – universal (basic, key) and special (professional, subject-based). Therefore, the issue of the formation of the competence of future specialists is the most topical problem in modern professional higher education.

The aim of the paper is to clarify the concept of PR competency and define the components of PR competency of future managers.

Modern pedagogical science defines competency as general capacity and readiness of personality to carry out activity that is based on expertise, which is acquired through training and oriented to independent participation of personality in training and a cognitive process [1, p. 41]. Expertise is aimed at successful entering of personality into professional activity [3, p. 23].

Competency is a set of professional knowledge and skills as well as the modes of professional activities where the core contains activity-oriented capacities – a set of action modes. According to researchers (V. Biluk, M. Golovan, O. Ponetun, O. Timets etc.), competency includes a set of personal interconnected capacities (knowledge, skills, activity modes) that are specified in relation to a certain list of academic subjects and processes where the capacities are necessary for qualitative seminal activity in relation to the academic subjects and processes [1, p. 46].

Some investigators consider the concept of competency a little narrower and derivative of the concept of competence. For example, A. Miheyenko considers the competency as a socially relevant educational result of the

implementation of competences, and N. Volkova – as a general ability that is based on knowledge, experience, values and abilities acquired through training [5, p. 88].

We absolutely agree with the national scientists K. Yuryeva and O. Tishchenko who claim that the concept of competency reflects the content of a certain kind of activity, while competence is a set of personality qualities necessary for the implementation of this content [8, p. 175] and together with O. Sadohin, consider the competence as a set of expertise and skills that allow the subject to effectively deal with problems and implement necessary actions in any field of activity, but the competency is a set of objective conditions that determine the possibilities and limits of the realization of personality competence [8, p. 175]

A professionally competent specialist is able to efficiently perform professional activity in accordance with social requirements for the profession and demonstrate appropriate personal qualities that are based on relevant knowledge, skills, emotions, motivation, commitment, moral and ethical values and experience, use knowledge for solving practical problems in accordance with their competency. Competencies guarantee productive implementation of professional activities and are the ability of a human to put into practice their competence.

As of a modern manager, the field of their professional activity is social-economic behavior of a human being. So, a manager's capacity to perform their duties means to skillfully run the company, to control behavior of people and establish links between the company and the community. It is possible to do so when a manager has certain communicative skills and public relations competency.

Modern science actively uses the concept of public relations (PR). Most researchers define PR as practical or professional activity (S. Black, E. Bernas, R. Harlow, D. Doty, V. Moiseev, G. Pocheptsov etc.). This approach means that PR is specific professional activity that is aimed at mutual understanding and well-wishing relationships between social agents, who can be personalities, groups of people, society in general as well as various organizations and industrial companies [9, p. 45]. To illustrate the approach, one more definition belongs to S. Black, English sociologist, who states that PR is art and science to analyse tendencies, the prophecy of consequences, the providing of recommendations to the authorities of company and the performance of programs and actions to benefit both the company and community [9, p. 15].

Therefore, according to researchers, PR is practical or professional activity of people who are involved into implementation of friendly relationships with community and provide recommendations to various organizations.

According to some researchers (F. Hesslow, T. Hunt, J. Grunig, V. Korolko, O. Tihomirova etc.), PR is communication between a company and its social environment or a form of the organization of communication. PR means understanding through knowledge. The protagonists of the approach define the gist of the concept of PR as «analysis, structure and control of communication flows of an institution (including a company) as well as the solution of the tasks of the communication management of society in general» [4, p. 14].

The PR phenomenon, which is defined by American Foundation for Public Relations Research and Education, is of interest for our research. The result of its analysis is a synthesised definition that embraces conceptual and operational aspects of relations with community: “Public relations is a special function of control that is aimed at the establishing and support of mutual relations, understanding, recognition and cooperation between the organization and its community; control of problem solutions or arguments; investigating the public opinion and providing feedback to help authorities; determining and emphasizing responsibility of authorities to contribute to social interests; effective changing in accordance with the demands of the times; timely notification to predict development tendencies; using scientific methods, which are based on ethical standards of communication as the basic tools”. [10, p. 36].

Taking into account the definitions of PR, professional competency, we state it that PR competency is an integral characteristic of the personality-based, professional and behavioural capacities of individual, an indicator of main psychological and PR concepts, a capacity to effectively use modern psychological and PR technologies that enable the specialist to guarantee their self-actualisation in profession to its maximum extent.

At present, PR activity is carried out in all the spheres of social life. The major aim of the PR activity of a company is to create an external and internal social-political-psychological medium that contributes to company's success, guarantees proper behaviour of the medium to benefit the company. Therefore, the PR activity of company can be divided into several areas that gravitate to various social groups (communities) or a proper objective (image of company, crisis negotiation, and turnover).

Requirements to professional competence can be presented as a professional profile of a future specialist, i.e. a certain set of professional competencies that guarantee maturation of a personality in general relying on intellectual, personal, emotional and social development.

The key national scholars-specialists in PR [6, p. 115] specify some major functions to guarantee good relationship with the public: to study the public opinion; to establish and promote two-way communication (company – community); to prevent conflicts; to promote and advertise goods and services; to create and support a positive image of company, goods, services as well as a corporate culture within the company.

The idea of V. Maslova, V. Siniaev and I. Siniaeva [7, p. 215] deserves a scrupulous look. Their proposal is to consider the system of a PR services market as in the formula:

$$SPR = f(C; O; A; I; R; G),$$

where C is communication that allows to rapidly establish real contacts between people, companies and organizations;

O – community as a relatively stable group of people who establish various contacts in various conditions of social life, mass consciousness, moral values and interests;

A – analysis that is built upon system research when using various forms and methods to estimate interaction environment to approve reasonable managerial decisions in order to establish the public opinion and successfully put PR strategies into practice;

I – image (a created image of company that corresponds to its mission, results and social significance);

R – company's reputation that is created at the expense of active participation in significant community's events of a social nature, popularity in a society, speeches in mass media;

G – harmony (major background for the subjects of market to interact to reach an agreement and collaborate in the course of business).

According to S. Black, the founder of the PR theory, PR business successfully employs people having certain personality-based and professional qualities. The most important ones, in the opinion of the researcher, are common sense, natural interest, capacities of good speaking and writing, flexibility, endurance, purposefulness, attention to insignificant matters, good upbringing and education [7, p.11].

The scholar F. Buari, a competent French authority in the field of PR, using an acmeology approach, includes a range of interconnected subsystems into the system of the components of PR competency, namely, personality professionalism, activity professionalism, normative regulation of activity and behavior, a productive self-concept [2, p. 112].

Each subsystem has its structural components (blocks) that are interconnected. So, the system of professional activity is a well-balanced combination of high professional competence, professional skills at the level of professional mastery as well as acmeological invariants of professionalism, which are special skills. According to F. Buari, professional competence is a system of knowledge that constantly increases and allows an expert to effectively perform their duties. It is what an expert has to know to work good [2, p. 114]. Professional skills are a major regulative component of an activity professionalism subsystem. The content of the skills is stipulated by professional duties of a PR expert, that's, what he must be capable to do [2, p. 115], by a place, functions and status in the system. An important thing here is that the skills are flexible, they allow to solve professional tasks in any situation, constantly increase, be advanced and based on a creative approach. For example, a PR expert is able to establish communication with people, make a good impression on them, implement various forms of business communication, persuade and influence them, make a dispute, use modern computer technologies, do some kinds of journalistic work (make press releases, reports etc.), analyze the data of sociological and psychological research etc.

The subsystem of personality professionalism, according to F. Buari, contains description and major requirements for various personality characteristics and qualities of the subject of labor that determine high efficiency of professional activity. The subsystem includes several interconnected substructures: personality capacities (intellectual, communicative, organizational, general managerial, psychological), professional qualities (good memory, trained attention, imagination, emotional stability, will, industriousness), professional and personality-based qualities (self-discipline, initiative, responsibility, discipline), creativity, a need for professional achievements [2, p. 118].

The subsystem of the norms of activity and behavior is the norms and rules that are a strong ethical regulator of behavior.

The subsystem of a productive self-image can be considered as the reflection of self [2, p. 120]. Adequate imagination of self – self-image – allows

us to formulate real and dynamic personality-based and professional standards, development and self-development programs, to build a harmonious and productive system of professional interaction and relationships. The basis of self-concept includes self-imagination at present time (I am), ideal self (I want to be), dynamic self (the way that changes will go), fantastic self (I would have been if...). Their harmonious integration is the basis for progressive development of expert.

On the basis of the analysis of scientific approaches to the definition of the concept of PR-competency and its content, we offer module of core competencies that in totality make the PR-competency of a future manager. In our opinion, this module of competencies will contain two clusters: key (common) and special (professional) competencies.

The cluster of key (common) competencies includes:

Having analyzed scientific approaches to the definition of the concept of PR competence and its meaning, we propose our model of PR competence. We believe that this cluster has to include the following major competencies, which are in the block of general cultural and professional competencies:

- the ability for cognitive activity, self-development and self-education;
- the ability to produce new ideas, innovative solutions and the ways of solving problem situations, to demonstrate creativity;
- skills to analyze and estimate social significant phenomena, events and processes;
- the ability to use informational and communicative technologies in professional activity;
- the ability to realize plans and be responsible for results of actions;
- capacity and readiness to conduct a dialogue on the basis of the values of a democratic society;
- skills to understand content, gist, major ideas, social significance of own activity, to aspire to improve this understanding through the use of knowledge in own practical activity;

The cluster of special (professional) competencies includes:

- use of major ways and means of information interaction; skills to logically, substantially and clearly build spoken and written language; capacity to effectively communicate, make speeches, negotiate, write business correspondence, use e-mail;
- knowledge and skills to adapt the best foreign and national PR practice to own professional activity;

- the ability to analyze, design and communicate with a person, in a group and an organization; ability to speak clearly, briefly, persuasively selecting appropriate style and content for a certain group;
- the ability to represent a company and present official information when interacting with the public, companies, state authorities and mass media;
- capacity to avoid and settle conflict situations when interacting with the public, companies, state authorities and mass media;
- the ability to find information to approve decisions when having a feedback in professional activity;
- capacity to understand major regularities and use basic technologies to form the public opinion;
- use of main technologies to establish and promote the image of company, to support a corporate culture of organization.

Conclusions. The gist of the concept of PR competence is clarified. It is an integral characteristic of personality-based, professional and behavioral qualities. PR competency is the knowledge of main PR concepts and ability to efficiently use modern PR technologies. We have determined main general cultural and professional competencies of a future manager.

We believe that the formation of the PR competency as a set of personality-based and professional resources that guarantee a possibility to efficiently solve professional tasks by an expert in the future will become a constituent of the training of a future manager.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

1. Білик В. В. Компетенції і компетентності як нові освітні конструкти / В.В. Білик // Педагогічний дискурс. — Випуск 7. — 2010. — С. 41-46.
2. Буари Ф. А. Паблік рилейшнз или стратегия доверия / Филипп А. Буари. — М. : Имидж-Контакт; Инфра-М, 2001. — 178 с.
3. Гушлевська І. Поняття компетентності у вітчизняній та зарубіжній педагогіці / І. Гушлевська // Шлях освіти. — 2004. — №3. — С. 22–24.
4. Королько В. Г. Паблік рилейшнз. Наукові основи, методика, практика / В. Г. Королько. — К. : Видавничий дім «Скарби», 2001. — 400 с.
5. Міхеєнко О. І. Професійна підготовка майбутніх фахівців зі здоров'я людини до застосування здоров'язміцнювальних технологій у контексті компетентнісного підходу / О. І. Міхеєнко // Засоби навчальної та науково-дослідної роботи : зб. наук. праць / за заг. ред. проф. В. І. Євдокимова і проф. О. М. Микитюка. — 2014. — Вип.42.— С. 85–97.

6. Почепцов Г. Г. Паблік рилейшнз / Г. Г. Почепцов. — К. : Знання, 2000. — 280 с.

7. Синяева И. М. Сфера PR в маркетинге / И. М. Синяева, В. М. Маслова, В. В. Синяев. — М. : ЮНИТИ-ДАНА, 2007. — 383 с.

8. Юр'єва К. А. Компетенція, компетентність, міжкультурна компетентність учителя: сутність і зміст / К. А. Юр'єва, О. М. Тіщенко // Засоби навчальної та науково-дослідної роботи : зб. наук. праць / за заг. ред. проф. В. І. Євдокімова і проф. О. М. Микитюка; Харк. нац. пед. ун-т імені Г. С. Сковороди. — 2014. — Вип.42. — С. 169–182.

9. Black S. The essentials of public relations // S. Black. — London : Kogan Page. — 1993. — 216 p.

10. Harlow R. F. Building a Public Relations Definition / R. F. Harlow // Public Relations Review. — 1976. — Winter. — Vol. 2. — № 4. — P. 36-44.

Моргунова С. О. Компоненти PR-компетенції майбутніх менеджерів.

У статті визначено суть PR-компетенції як складової професійної компетентності майбутнього менеджера. Виходячи з тлумачення понять «PR» («зв'язки з громадськістю»), «професійна компетенція», автор дає своє визначення PR-компетенції як інтегральної сукупності особистісних, професійних і поведінкових якостей особистості, показника знання основних психологічних і PR-концепцій, показника вміння ефективно використовувати сучасні психологічні та PR-технології, що дозволяють фахівцю максимально реалізуватися в професії. Автор зазначає, що особливо значущою наявність PR-компетенції є для майбутніх менеджерів, оскільки до кола професійних завдань сучасного фахівця цього напряму входить управління репутацією організації, просування її продукту на ринку, здійснення зв'язків зі споживачами та ЗМІ, формування позитивного іміджу організації та її внутрішнього корпоративного середовища. На основі проведеного аналізу наукових підходів до визначення поняття PR-компетенції та її змісту запропоновано блок основних компетенцій, що містить два кластера: групу ключових (загальних) та групу спеціальних (фахових) компетенцій, поєднання яких складає PR-компетенцію майбутнього менеджера.

Ключові слова: паблік рилейшнз, компетентнісний підхід, компетенція, компетентність, PR-компетенція.

Моргунова С. А. Компоненты PR-компетенции будущих менеджеров.

В статье определяется суть PR-компетенции как составляющей профессиональной компетентности будущего менеджера. Исходя из толкования понятий «PR» («связи с общественностью»), «профессиональная компетенция», автор дает свое определение PR-компетенции как интегральной совокупности личностных, профессиональных и поведенческих качеств личности, показателя знания основных психологических и PR-концепций, показателя умения эффективно использовать современные психологические и PR-технологии, позволяющие специалисту максимально реализоваться в профессии. Автор отмечает, что особенно значимой наличие PR-компетенции является для будущих менеджеров, поскольку в круг профессиональных задач современного специалиста этого направления входит управление репутацией организации, продвижения ее продукта на рынке, осуществление связей с потребителями и СМИ, формирования положительного имиджа организации и ее внутренней корпоративной среды. На основе проведенного анализа научных подходов к определению понятия PR-компетенции и ее содержания предложено блок основных компетенций, включающий два кластера: группу ключевых (общих) и группу специальных компетенций, сочетание которых составляет PR-компетенцию будущего менеджера.

Ключевые слова: публик рилейшнз, компетентностный подход, компетенция, компетентность, PR-компетенция.

REFERENCES

1. Bilyk V. V. Kompetentsiyi i kompetentnosti yak novi osvitni konstrukty [Competences of competence as new educational constructs] / V. V. Bilyk // Pedahohichnyy dyskurs. — Vypusk 7. — 2010. — S. 41–46.
2. Buari F. A. Pablik rileyshnz ili strategija doverija [Public relations or strategy Trust] / Filipp A. Buari. — M. : Imidzh-Kontakt; Infra-M, 2001. — 178 s.
3. Hushlevs'ka I. Ponyattya kompetentnosti u vitchyznyaniy ta zarubizhniy pedahohitsi [Concept of competence of domestic and foreign pedagogics] / I. Hushlevs'ka // Shlyakh osvity. — 2014. — № 3. — S. 22–24.
4. Korol'ko V. H. Pablyk rileyshnz. Naukovi osnovy, metodyka, praktyka [Public Relations. Scientific bases, technique, practice] / V. H. Korol'ko. — K. : Vydavnychyu dim “Skarby”, 2001. — 400 s.
5. Mikheyenko O. I. Profesiyna pidhotovka maybutnikh fakhivtsiv zi zdorov"ya lyudyny do zastosuvannya zdorov"yazmitsnyuval'nykh tekhnolohiy u konteksti kompetentnisnoho pidkhodu [Professional training of future specialists in the field of human health towards the of health improving technologies in the context of a competence approach] / O. I. Mikheyenko // Zasoby navchal'noyi ta naukovo-

doslidnoyi roboty : zb. nauk. prats' / za zah. red. prof. V. I. Yevdokymova i prof. O. M. Mykytyuka. — Vyp. 42. — Kharkiv : KhNPU imeni H. S. Skovorody, 2014. — S. 85–97.

6. Pocheptsov H. H. Pablyk ryleyshnz. [Public Relations] / H. H. Pocheptsov. — K. : Znannya, 2000. — 280 c.

7. Sinjaeva I. M. Sfera PR v marketinge [The sphere of PR in marketing] / I. M. Sinjaeva, V. M. Maslova, V. V. Sinjaev. — M. : JuNITI-DANA, 2007. — 383 s.

8. Yuryeva K. A. Kompetentsiya, kompetentnist', mizhkul'turna kompetentnist' uchytelya: sutnist' i zmist [The sphere of competence, competence, teacher's inter-cultural competence: essence and content] / K. A. Yuryeva, O. M. Tishchenko // Zasoby navchal'noyi ta naukovo-doslidnoyi roboty : zb. nauk. prats' / za zah. red. prof. V. I. Yevdokymova i prof. O. M. Mykytyuka — Vyp. 42. — Kharkiv : KhNPU imeni H. S. Skovorody, 2014. — S. 169–182.

9. Black S. The essentials of public relations // S. Black. — London : Kogan Page. — 1993. — 216 p.

10. Harlow Rex F. Building a Public Relations Definition / R. F. Harlow // Public Relations Review. — 1976, Winter. — Vol. 2. — № 4. — P. 36–44.